

EFFICACY OF SADHYA VAMAN IN URDHVAGA AMLAPITTA CAUSED BY AGNIMANDYA: A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Urdhvaga Amlapitta, a condition characterized by excessive acid production in the upper gastrointestinal tract, is often linked to Agnimandya. This case study evaluates the efficacy of Sadhya Vaman (therapeutic emesis) in managing Urdhvaga Amlapitta caused by Agnimandya. A 38 year old male patient presented with symptoms of Urdhvaga Amlapitta, including Hrudadaha(heartburn), regurgitation, and Hrullas (nausea), Aruchi, Avipaka, AmlaUdgara since 1.5 years attributed to Agnimandya. He underwent Sadhya Vaman therapy by using Dugdha, Lavanodaka, Madanphala pippali churna and Madhu. After Sadhya Vaman, the patient showed significant improvement in symptoms, with reduced Hrudadaha(heartburn), regurgitation, and Hrullas (nausea), Shiroshool, Aruchi, Avipaka, AmlaUdgara improved digestion, and relief from discomfort. Sadhya Vaman therapy appears

effective in managing Urdhvaga Amlapitta caused by Agnimandya, offering a potential treatment approach for this condition.

KEYWORDS: Urdhvaga Amlapitta, Agnimandya, Sadhya Vaman, Therapeutic Emesis. a, APM's Ayurved Mahavidyalaya Sion.

INTRODUCTION

“Rogo sarveapi mandeagnau” Acharya Vagbhaṭa has described that all the diseases are

caused by MandAgni. In Ayurved main cause of all disease is MandAgni.^[1] Generally 80% of the top ten life threatening diseases in the world are due to inappropriate dietary habits.^[2] Amlapitta explained as separate disease by Acharya Kashyap, Yogratnakar, Bhavprakash, Madhavnidan. Charak explained Shuktapaka in purvarupa of Grahani which is sampitta/Amlapitta related.^[3] In Madhav nidan Due to increase in amla gun there is increase in pitta so it called as Amlapitta. In Sharangdhara pratham khanda according to gati bheda amlapiita divided as Urdhvaga and Adhoga.^[4] As per Acharya Sushruta, improperly digested food becomes poisonous or toxic (shukta/ anna-vish), this toxic-juice / shukta combines with pachaka-pitta and creates a variety of pitta-dominant diseases.^[5] Madhavkar explained Causes of Amlapitta in madhav nidan chap51/.^[6]

विरुद्ध-दुष्ट-अम्ल-विदाहि-पित्त-प्रकोपि-विदाहि-अन्नभोजातविदग्धम्।
पित्तं स्वविचारितं यत्तद् अम्लपित्तं प्रवदन्ति सन्तः॥१॥”

Symptoms of Amlapitta given in Madav nidan 51/2.^[7]

अविपाकःक्लमोउत्क्लेशःतिक्ताम्लोद्गारगौरवम्।
हृत्कण्ठदाहारुचिभिश्चाम्लपित्तं वदेद्विषक् ॥२॥”

Symptoms of Urdhvaga Amlapitta given in Madav nidan 51/4-6.^[8]

वान्तं हरितपीतकनीलकृष्णमारक्तरक्ताभमतीव चाम्लम् । मांसोदकाभं तन्तुविच्छिलाच्छिं श्लेष्मान्वितं वा
विविधं वमेत् ॥४॥ भुक्ते विदग्धे तथाऽप्यभुक्ते करोति तिक्ताम्लवमि कदाचित् ।
उद्गारमेविधमेव कण्ठहृत्ककुक्षिदाहं शिरसो रुजं च ॥५॥ करपाददाहमौष्यं मितीमरुचिं ज्वरं
च कफपित्तम् । जनयति [१] कण्डूमण्डलविद्रधिपिडका तनुचितगात्ररोगान् ॥६॥

In Amlapitta the root cause is Agnimandya and formation of Aama. In Yogratnakara Amlapitta chikitsa given as^[9]

“वमितस्यवमनकर्मणःपश्चात्तदुद्विरेचनम्।
कुर्वन्ति विरिक्तस्य स्नेहस्निग्धस्य अनुवासनम्॥”

A CASE REPORT

Patient Name- ABC Age- 38years

Sex- Male

Address - Khaparidev chs parel, Mumbai

C/O- Hrudadaha(heartburn), regurgitation, and Hrullas (nausea), Shiroshool, Aruchi, Avipaka, AmlaUdgara since 1.5 years. Taken oral medication for same complaints but got only temporary relief. Hence to take Ayurvedic Panchakarma treatment he came to our Opd

of Panchakarma department.

- **Personal History-** Occupation- Pharma Company MR Addiction- Tea 5-6 per day
Family History- No any evidence of such symptoms in family. Past History-No H/O- HTN/DM/KOCH'S
No Any surgical history

- **General examination- Systemic Examination**

General condition- Good CVS-S1S2 normal Bp- 130/80mmhg CNS- conscious oriented P- 84/min RS- AEBE clear

Spo2- 98% on RA P/A- Soft, Non tender Pallor- Absent.

Ashtavidh Parikshan- Nadi- Pitta Kapha Mala- prakrut

Mutra- Samyak pravrutti Jivha- Ishat saam Shabda – Spashta

Sparsha – samashitoshana Drik- Prakrut

Aakruti- Madhyam Samprapti Ghatak

Dosha - Pitta Pradhana, Kapha anubandhi. Dushya -Rasa Dushti.

Strotodushti- Annavaha Strotas, Purishvaha Strotas, Rasavaha Strotas. Vyadhi Avastha- Sama Avastha, Dosha Urdhwagati

Sadhyasadhyatva- Kashta Sadhya Vyadhimarga- Abhyantar Marga

Vyadhi Nidana - Urdhwaga Amlapitta, Samawastha Dosha Urdhwagati.

DIAGNOSIS

Based on Symptoms the patient was diagnosed with Urdhvaga Amlapitta.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Sadhya Vaman Material

Vaman Pitha, Chair, Bucket, Madanphal pippali churna, Makshik, Yashtimadhu Phant, Lavnodaka, Dugdha. Glass 2-3, Bowl, til tail.

Pre-procedure (Purva Karma)

- ✓ Informed written consent was taken from the patient after thoroughly explaining the details of the Vaman procedure.
- ✓ Local Snehan Swedan at chest region done.
- ✓ Dugdhan^[10] given to patient approx. 250-500ml.

Procedure (Pradhan Karma)

- ✓ As Vaman yog given Madanphala^[11] pippali churna with makshik.
- ✓ Then after waiting for 10 min we given Yashtimadhu phant.^[12]
- ✓ After that Vaman vega started.
- ✓ Approx 2lit of Yashtimadhu phant used.
- ✓ After that approx 500ml Lavnodaka given.^[12]
- ✓ The dormant urge may be excited by tickling the throat with two fingers^[13]
- ✓ At the last vega pitta darshana observed.^[14]
- ✓ During procedure patient was vitally stable.

Post-procedure (Paschat Karma)

- ✓ After the therapy has been well-administered, the patient was asked to wash his hands, feet and face with warm water.
- ✓ Dhumpan(herbal smoking) given to patient.^[15]
- ✓ Then patient was asked to rest in a room which is not exposed to the wind.
- ✓ Patient asked to take rest for some time.
- ✓ Patient advised to follow sansarjan kram for 5 days.

RESULTS/ OBSERVATION

After Sadhya Vaman, the patient showed significant improvement in symptoms, with reduced Hrudadaha(heartburn), regurgitation, and Hrullas (nausea), Shiroshool, Aruchi, Avipaka, AmlaUdgara improved digestion, and relief from discomfort.

Manki Parikshan- Total intake 3000ml (Dugdha 500ml, Yashtimadhu Phant 2000ml, Lavnodaka 500ml)

Total outcome – 3200ml

Antiki Parikshan- Pittanta vaman

Laigiki Parikshan- Strotoshuddhi, Shirolaghavta, Kanthashuddhi.^[16] Vaigiki Parikshan- 7 uttam vega, 3 madhyam vega.

After assessment Samyak vaman karma (mandhyam shuddhi) is seen in patient. Vaman Karma

ASSESSMENT

After Vaman				
Symptoms	Before vaman	0th day	7th day	21thday
Hrudadaha(heartburn)	+++	-	-	-
Hrullas (nausea)	++	-	-	-
Aruchi	+	-	-	-
Avipaka	+	-	-	-
AmlaUdgara	++	-	-	-
Regurgitation	+++	+	-	-
Shiroshool	++		-	

DISCUSSION

After Sadhya Vaman patient got relief from symptoms and after taking follow up for one month patient had no any recurrence in same symptoms. In this case due to irregular schedule and improper diet habit agnimandya occur and after that due to continue vidahi diet intake symptoms of amlapitta occur, As samprapti given in kashyapa khilstan 16/7-13.

Hetu sevan

(Irregular meal Time/Fast food/Vidahi annapan/Tea) Tridosha Prakopa (Pitta Pradhana)

Agnimandya

Anna Vidagdhata Pittataprakop (vitiation)

Amla and Drava Guna dominance Amlapitta.

Breakdown Of Pathogenesis and Urdhvaga Amlapitta with Vaman

Procedure Effect

Urdhvaga Amlapitta Occur in Amashaya

□

Amashayastha Dosh Sanchit Avastha

□

Dosha Expulsion by vaman therapy

□

Agnimandya

□

Anna vidagdhata

□

Pitta prakop, amla, drava gun

□

Amlapitta Upashaya

Vaman Dravyas are having the properties Vyavayi and Vikasi by virtue of Veerya (Potency) they circulate quickly in to large and small capillaries of the body. It circulate all over the body. Doshas started melting in the body due to Ushna Guna, we can observe the perspiration (Swede Pradurbhava) on patient's forehead or sometimes whole body. Because of its Vikashi Guna, it detaches the Malas from Dhatus. Owing to the presence of Sukshma Guna and Anupravana properties the Malas or Doshas float because already body has got Samyak Snigdhatta (internal oleation) and pass through smallest capillaries and ultimately Malarupi Kapha reaches to stomach due to which agnimandya happened. Vamana Karma is radical therapy to treat Kapha disease. Vamana karma corrects the pathology by eliminating disease causative factor Kapha from its main site of accumulation. Vamana cleanses the different types of toxic materials from the body. Vamana karma one of the purification therapies restores the Agni(impaired metabolism) by acting at cellular level, there by correcting acid secretion and vamana action.^[17] after the vamana therapy, no recurrence of any symptom was observed during follow ups. Shodhan Chikitsa(Purification Therapy) facilitates the expulsion of vitiated Dosha from the body, there by cures the disease from root. Thus Shodhan Chikitsa can prevent the recurrence in future.^[18]

CONCLUSION

Based on this case Sadhya Vaman therapy appears effective in managing Urdhvaga Amlapitta caused by Agnimandya, offering a potential treatment approach for this condition.

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